

Table S1. Model performance, full eligible cohort aged 45-75 years, BRFSS 2024

Model	AUC (95% CI)	Brier score (95% CI)	Calibration intercept	Calibration slope	AUC, unweighted (DeLong)^a
XGBoost (primary, survey-weighted)	0.737 (0.731 to 0.743)	0.1753 (0.1733 to 0.1773)	-0.004	0.993	0.728
Spline + SDoH logistic	0.737 (0.731 to 0.742)	0.1754 (0.1734 to 0.1774)	-0.008	0.991	0.727
LASSO logistic	0.683 (0.677 to 0.689)	0.1963 (0.1940 to 0.1986)	-0.365	0.429	0.671
XGBoost (unweighted, sensitivity)	0.74 (0.735 to 0.746)	0.1743 (0.1723 to 0.1762)	0.021	1.022	0.731
Age-only (RCS logistic, reference)	0.685 (0.678 to 0.691)	NA	NA	NA	NA

SDoH increment over age-only (XGBoost): +0.052 (95% CI +0.048 to +0.056), $P < .001$.

SDoH increment over age-only (spline logistic, secondary): +0.052 (95% CI +0.048 to +0.056), $P < .001$.

Analytic $n = 227,647$; weighted outcome prevalence, 29.8%. Weighted AUC and weighted Brier score are reported with design-based bootstrap 95% CIs (primary sampling units within strata); calibration intercept and slope are weighted.

^a Unweighted DeLong AUC, reported as a secondary reference.

Abbreviations: AUC, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve; CI, confidence interval; LASSO, least absolute shrinkage and selection operator; RCS, restricted cubic spline; SDoH, social determinants of health.

Table S2. Outcome decomposition: never-screened versus overdue, established-eligible adults aged 50-75 years, BRFSS 2024

Separate binary models against the up-to-date reference in the primary established-eligible cohort (ages 50-75). Weighted AUC with design-based bootstrap 95% CI (PSU within strata); weighted Brier score; leading predictors ranked by mean absolute SHAP value (log-odds).

Delay state	Analytic n	Weighted prevalence, %	Weighted AUC (95% CI)	Weighted Brier	Leading predictors (by mean absolute SHAP)
Never screened vs up to date	185,484	19.2	0.746 (0.739 to 0.753)	0.133	education, age, household income, employment
Overdue vs up to date	170,343	8.4	0.544 (0.533 to 0.556)	0.077	household income, Census region, race/ethnicity, marital status

Abbreviations: AUC, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve; CI, confidence interval; SHAP, Shapley additive explanations.

Note: the pooled screening-delay outcome combines both states. The never-screened model discriminated well and was led by access and resource determinants; the overdue model performed near chance, consistent with a continuity-of-care mechanism distinct from first access.